

A STUDY OF EFFECT OF CRITICAL THINKING ON LOGICAL LEARNING OF B. ED. TEACHER TRAINEES OF B.Ed. COLLEGE

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Abstract

Critical thinking is thinking more deeply. It involves reasoning logically and analyzing, organizing, examining and questioning information to attain several possible answers rather than focusing on finding just the correct answers. critical thinking is focused on deciding what to believe or do. This definition allows flexibility and diversity of application including decision-making, problem solving, value judgment. The study has been delimited to the B. Ed. Teacher Trainees of Teacher Education Institutions affiliated to North Gujarat University. The population of the study was the B. Ed. Teacher Trainees of North Gujarat. The sample for the study was selected by using random sampling and total 88 teacher trainee were selected for the present study during the year of 2021. Data for the present investigation the investigator had constructed the Creative Thinking Test form the alternatives measurements. Data for the present research was collected by the investigator by test and retest method (Retest was applied to theories the trainee of application of critical thinking). The researcher had employed the formulas of Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-value. The study has been delimited to find out the effect of variables of gender, sample from Grant-in-aid college of North Gujarat region. Research it is found that mean score of all B. Ed. Teacher Trainees, male B. Ed. Teacher Trainees and female teacher trainee are found significant on retest of on achievement test based on critical thinking.

Key words: Critical thinking

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Introduction:

According to psychology we all are unique because we can think and we all are different because we can think. The unique difference between a human being and an animal is the ability to think and to use cognitive skills. Development of thinking has been one of the important and commonly expressed aims of education. Thinking has been defined as "going beyond the information given" (Bruner 1957); as a complex and high level skill "that fill ups gaps in the evidence" (Bruner 1957); and as a process of searching through a problem space" (Newel and Simon 1972); and as what we do" when we are doubt about how to act, what to believe or what to decide" (Baron 1994). The term "critical" is derived from ancient Greek. The word "critical" derives etymologically from two Greek roots "Kriticos" (meaning discerning) and "kriterian" (meaning standard). Etymologically, then the word implies development of "discerning judgment based on standard". In Webster's New world dictionary, "careful analysis and judgment" and is followed by the gloss; "critical" in its strictest sense, implies an attempt at objective judgment so as to determine the both merits and faults. Critical thinking is thinking more deeply. It involves reasoning logically and analyzing, organizing, examining and questioning information to attain several possible answers rather than focusing on finding just the correct answers. The concept of critical thinking as defined by Robert Ennis (1985) states that critical thinking is focused on deciding what to believe or do. This definition allows flexibility and diversity of application including decision-making, problem solving, value judgment and higher levels of Bloom (1974) Taxonomy.

Statement of the Problem:

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Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the present research were:

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To study the effectiveness of 'Critical Thinking' on logical learning of B. Ed. Teacher Trainees by test and retest method.

To study the effectiveness of 'Critical Thinking' on logical learning of B. Ed. Teacher Trainees by test and retest method with variable of Male Trainees.

To study the effectiveness of 'Critical Thinking' on logical learning of B. Ed. Teacher Trainees by test and retest method with variable of Female Trainees.

Hypotheses of the study:

Hypotheses of the present investigation were:

Ho.1: There will be no significant difference between mean score of test and retest group of B. Ed. Teacher Trainees on achievement test.

Ho.2: There will be no significant difference between mean score of test and retest of male B. Ed. Teacher Trainees on achievement test.

Ho.3: There will be no significant difference between mean score of test and retest of female B. Ed. Teacher Trainees on achievement test.

Variables of the Study: Variables of the present research study were:

<u>Sr. No.</u>	<u>Type of Variables</u>	<u>Variables under the Investigation</u>
1.	Dependent Variable	Creative Thinking
2.	Independent Variable	Logical learning
3.	Moderate Variables	Gender

Operational Definitions of the Terms:

Critical Thinking: defined by Bayer (1985) it is determining the authenticity, accuracy and worth of information or knowledge claims. A few dimension of critical thinking that was considered for the study are given as follows. Comparing analogous problem situations, Evaluating actions, Abilities of reasoning, Abilities of decision making, Analysis of beliefs, Arguments of theories

Delimitations of the Study:

The study has been delimited to the B. Ed. Teacher Trainees of Teacher Education Institutions affiliated to North Gujarat University. The study has been delimited to find out the effect of variables of gender.

Research Area:

The present research study was conducted taking sample from Grant-in-aid college of North Gujarat region.

Research Design:

The present research was experimental by its nature.

Population and Sample of the Study:

The population of the study was the B. Ed. Teacher Trainees of North Gujarat. The sample for the study was selected by using random sampling and total 60 teacher trainee were selected for the present study during the year of 2021.

Tools of the Study:

To collect the data for the present investigation the investigator had constructed the Creative Thinking programme and Test form the alternatives measurements.

Data Collection:

Data for the present research was collected by the investigator by test and retest method (Retest was applied to theories the trainee of application of critical thinking).

Statistical Treatment:

For the calculation of the data, the researcher had employed the formulas of Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-value.

Data Analysis:

The sample of 88 B. Ed. Teacher Trainees from North Gujarat were studied on Creative Thinking Scale. The tabulation and statistical calculations were made for analysis and interpretations of data of test as well as re-test of the experimental design of the study. The t-test was employed for the comparison of retest groups.

Findings of the study

- Mean score of retest are significantly higher than the mean score of test group of B. Ed. Teacher Trainees on Achievement test of critical thinking.
- Mean score of retest are significantly higher than the mean score of test group of male B. Ed. Teacher Trainees on Achievement test of critical thinking.
- Mean score of retest are significantly higher than the mean score of test female B. Ed. Teacher Trainees on Achievement test of critical thinking.

Conclusion

From the above research it is found that mean score of all B. Ed. Teacher Trainees, male B. Ed. Teacher Trainees and female teacher trainee are found significant on retest of on achievement test based on critical thinking.

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